

Original Article

A study of Business Environment and employee health

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ABSTRACT-

Among the various workplace concerns, employees' mental health and job performance are two of the most important factors. In a developed economy, both of these factors are focused on mental health affects employee performance. Mental health and stress affect high blood pressure, Diabetes and cardiovascular disease. High stress levels may also be associated with a higher risk of mental illness. Having a positive workplace environment increases employees' affection for the business organization and the ability to work. This paper aims to explore the impact of the workplace environment on employee health and productivity. If the workplace environment is right, it helps to increase efficiency but the hostile environment has a negative effect on performance. The environment in the workplace is related to employee stress and health. The favorable environment creates affection and commitment in the minds of the employees. The ability to achieve the goals of the organization increases the ability of the employees to work and commitment. The favorable environment increases the ability of the employees to work. There is a close relationship between employee productivity and health, so management should take care that employees do not suffer fatigue, illness or injury. Taking care of the health of employees helps increase the productivity of the companies and has good effects on the business.

Key words: Employee, health, environment, performance, Employee welfare, Types of environment.

Research methodology -

The research is a literature based study investigation the current issue. Paralarally we also relied on secondary data from various journals, authentic websites and internet.

Object-

- 1) To determine the use of job aid toward employees' performance
- 2) To determine whether physical work environment has influence on employee performance
- 3) To examine whether supervisor support contributes toward employees' performance

INTRODUCTION

Environment and human beings are closely related. If the surrounding environment is inappropriate, insecurity arises. Human life is difficult. The productivity of employees decreases. Employee productivity in the workplace environment is important to increase morale. Management should strive to create a conducive environment. The most important factor affecting the performance of employees is health. As health, there should be favorable conditions in the workplace for safety. If an employee is in a stressful situation

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for a long time, his health affects family and social life. Performance decreases Stress arises for many reasons where quick decisions have to be made, there is the most stressful environment.

Workplace environments include physical and behavioral factors Excellence in the work environment employee and labor efforts do the work necessary to determine productivity and performance levels. The employee's engagement with the organization and his behavior and communication all depend on the environment. Employee productivity is an important factor that depends on the work environment. Employees play positive or negative roles depending on the work environment. In developing countries, most workplace environments are safe and harmful. Workplace environment Workers to personally shape employee behavior Resulting employees' motivation to work hard Their performance and performance are shaped by the impact of their quality in the workplace Emotional commitment among employees Build trust loyalty among employees A healthy and safe work environment plays an important role in increasing productivity . Most professionals tend to ignore having a comfortable work environment, mistaking this as an additional expense.

If employees are willing and open to work, their productivity is likely to increase and the necessary equipment resources should be made available to work Independent operations are needed to analyze employee performance The key problem facing the business is improving employee performance and it is important to identify excellent employees and inefficient employees. Several important variables in the study and implementation of the performance assessment model have been found to be incorrect.

Business environment

Business Environment is Sum or collection of all internal and external factor such as employees customer needs and expectations supply and demand management clients supplier owner activities by government innovation in technology social trades market trends economic change etc.

Components of business environment

- 1) Economic environment
- 2) Political environment
- 3) Social environment
- 4) Technological environment
- 5) legal Environment

Types of environment Internal environment

a) Value system value system is important on the choice of business the mission and objective of the organization , business policies and practices.

b) Mission and objective

The business domain of the company ,priorities, direction of development , business philosophy business policy etc are guided by the mission and objective of the company.

c) Management structure and nature

Management structure are important factor every Organization some management structure delay in decision making.

D) Internal power relationship

In organization different level of employee, Shareholder and Board of director have important factor impact on the decision.

E) Other

Human resources, company image and Equity ,miscellaneous factor etc,

2) External macro environment

It includes success, strategies and decision making etc.

3) External micro environment

The micro environment consists of actors in the company immediate environment that effect the performance of the company. Its includes supplier marketing, intermediate, competitor customer and the public

Employee health

Employee health en compasses the physical and mental status of your employee physical health comes in to mind first but mental health is just as important.

Unhealthy environment

Some common symptoms for identifying an uncomfortable event environment include:

- 1) Employees have a high level of stress
- 2) Increased employee absenteeism rates reduce turnover rates
- 3) Job dissatisfaction increases and morale declines
- 4) Lack of communication between employees and management
- 5) Lack of employee appreciation
- 6) Employees lack trust
- 7) Employees are discriminated against

Changes needed for a healthy environment

1. To employee welfare Importance should be given

2. The need for open communication between employees and management
3. Encouraging employee morale to do better
4. A positive work culture must be developed.
5. Creating flexible work arrangements
6. There should be no discrimination.

Employee Health vs. Occupational Health

1) Occupational Health Care

Health care is provided to employees by the business organization but in many cases immediate and urgent care is not provided here due to outdated technology, employee records are not kept properly.

2) Employee Health Care

Various programs and services for employee well-being are made available from business organizations. Employee health services include physical examination, vaccination, hearing test, tuberculosis test, drugs, and alcohol testing. Some companies use cloud-based systems.

3) Welfare Programme

Welfare programs are created to reduce spending on health services and promote employee health. This program increases productivity, reduces employee absenteeism, and employees stay in the organization.

Employee welfare

The absence of employees in a business organization can lead to harm. By using a corporate wellness program, workplace well-being will be promoted for employees. Employee welfare includes the following elements at work.

- 1) Overall quality in the workplace
- 2) Workplace safety
- 3) Work environment
- 4) The workplace environment is when an employee is aware of his or her work.
- 5) Management of the organization

Employees should be physically and mentally healthy to achieve workplace well-being in a business organization, they should be satisfied only if they are safe while working. Employee welfare is affected by many factors; these factors are as follows:

1) Burnout employees are stressed

Due to workload due to many reasons e.g. wrong planning, The deadline given by the management, reduces the number of employees, etc.

2) Financial stress

Employees feel short of money as expenses increase, so loans are taken, all these factors put financial stress on the employees, which leads to depressive sleep, weight loss etc.

3) Social factors

Employee likes to live in society. If there is a lack of friendship or social relationships, the employee feels lonely in the workplace and therefore does not feel enthusiastic about working.

4) Poor workplace conditions

There should be enough sunlight and sanitation in the workplace but many times these facilities are not available. Improper use of space in the office. Lack of privacy.

5) Poor physical and mental health

Employees' physical and mental health needs to be good but many times the business organization environment does not provide good health to employees. Work stress or dissatisfaction often affects employees.

CONCLUSION

Workplace environment affects work in a poor environment, an employee may not be able to do work efficiently. This research paper contributes towards the welfare of the society as the result creates awareness about the importance of the good working environment for employee job satisfaction. Management should encourage employees not to put any kind of pressure; it results in reduced efficiency. A good environment is beneficial for both the organization and the employee.

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